

Tutorial: Hardware Failure Prediction for Cloud Service Reliability

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Duration: half a day.

Abstract—As cloud services become increasingly integral to modern computing, the reliability of underlying hardware components is critical to maintaining service continuity and performance. This tutorial delves into advanced methodologies for predicting hardware failures to cloud service reliability. We begin with an overview of hardware failures in data centers, followed by machine learning-based failure prediction methods designed for different hardware components. Key topics include hardware metrics for predictive analysis, feature engineering, algorithm selection, evaluation, and production deployment. In addition to knowledge share, the tutorial offers a hands-on Memory Failure Prediction competition, where participants apply their techniques to real-world problems. This tutorial is beneficial for researchers and engineers from both academia and industry, providing them with useful tools and necessary knowledge to enhance hardware resilience and cloud service reliability.

I. INTRODUCTION

In ever-growing datacenters, millions of servers operate together to meet the rising demand for cloud computing, big data storage, and AI computing tasks. With numerous tasks including resource-intensive AI computations running on these servers, hardware failures significantly impact the servers' Reliability, Availability and Serviceability (RAS) [1], [5]. In this tutorial, we explore cutting-edge methodologies for predicting hardware failures in cloud environments to ensure uninterrupted service continuity and optimal performance.

Hardware failure prediction, also known as predictive maintenance, is a proactive approach to mitigating potential hardware issues before they occur. In this tutorial, we will delve into state-of-the-art predictive approaches designed to bolster system resilience, with a specific focus on key hardware categories such as Dynamic Random Access Memory (DRAM) [7]–[9], High-Bandwidth Memory (HBM) [6], Hard Disk Drives (HDD) [3], and Optical transceiver [4]. The relevant approaches have been implemented and validated within a cloud environment.

We will begin by providing an overview of common hardware failures in data centers, highlighting the unique challenges faced by cloud environments. Next, we will examine system design considerations for handling hardware faults in the cloud, followed by an in-depth discussion of machine learning (ML)-based failure prediction techniques for different hardware types. The tutorial will cover essential topics such as hardware architecture, metrics for predictive analysis, feature

engineering, algorithm selection, evaluation, and the practicalities of deploying these models in production environments.

To complement the theoretical knowledge shared, this tutorial will also offer a hands-on experience: a **Memory Failure Prediction competition** [2]. In this competition, participants will have the opportunity to apply the concepts and techniques covered in the tutorial to solve real-world hardware failure problems. We will provide datasets, a starter kit, and an overview of memory systems to help participants get started. The competition aims to foster innovation in the field of failure prediction, with top-performing participants to share their solutions.

This tutorial aimed to academic researchers and industry professionals, particularly those involved in cloud computing, data centers, and hardware systems. Our objective is to provide participants with the tools, knowledge, and practical experience necessary to improve hardware resilience and, consequently, improve the reliability of cloud services. Given the growing relevance of this topic at the intersection of computer architecture and machine learning, this tutorial fills a crucial gap by offering a comprehensive exploration of the methods, applications, and challenges in this rapidly evolving field.

II. TARGET AUDIENCE AND REQUIREMENTS

The tutorial targets for researchers and engineers in the field of system reliability and machine learning. The participants are expected to have a basic understanding of computer architecture, hardware errors and machine learning. If not, we also provide intuitive descriptions for interested participants during the tutorial. Anyone excited about ML for system is welcome. The expected audience size is around 50 to 150. No special technical equipment is needed and some way of taking notes is suggested.

III. AGENDA

The tutorial is mainly organized and based on the recently published papers [4], [6]–[9] conducted by speakers. The topics cover the major hardware components in data centers, including DRAM, HBM, HDD, and optical transceiver. The outline is sketched as follows.

- Introduction (Min Zhou, **20 min**)
 - Overview of hardware failures in datacenters
 - Motivation
 - Business application
- Memory Failure Prediction (Qiao Yu, **30 min**)

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- Background of memory failure
- Hierarchical memory failure prediction [7]–[9]
- Conclusion and future work
- HBM Failure Prediction and Reliable Storage System (Zhirong Shen, **30 min**)
 - Introduce analysis of HBM errors in the field
 - Introduce HBM failure prediction framework
 - Introduce some techniques for reliable storage
- Competition Highlights (Min Zhou **30 min**)
 - Overview of the competition
 - Introduction to the SmartMem dataset
 - Attempts to the unified failure prediction framework
 - Open discussion and wrap-up
- Hands-on Online Competition(60 min)

Slides is available on the tutorial homepage (https://hwcloud-ras.github.io/HW_RAS-tutorial-HPCA-2025.github.io/) for public access.

IV. ORGANIZERS

A. Presenters

- **Qiao Yu** is currently a fourth-year PhD candidate at the Technical University of Berlin, jointly supervised by Prof. Jorge Cardoso and Prof. Odej Kao. His primary research interests are AIOPs, Hardware Failure Prediction, and Memory Reliability. He has published several papers at prestigious conferences, such as DSN, ICCAD, etc.
- **Min Zhou** is currently a Research Scientist in Huawei, China. She received the Ph.D. degree from Industrial Systems Engineering and Management Department, National University of Singapore in 2016. Her interests include pattern mining and machine learning, and their applications in sequence and graph data. She authored 20 patents and published over 30 research papers at prestigious conferences and journals.
- **Zhirong Shen** is currently a researcher in Xiamen University, Xiamen, China. He received the B.S. degree in University of Electronic Science and Technology of China in 2010, and the Ph.D. degree from Tsinghua University in 2016, respectively. His interests include storage systems and computer architectures. He has published over 70 research papers at prestigious conferences (e.g., HPCA, USENIX ATC, and ICDE) and journals (e.g., IEEE/ACM TON, ACM TOS, IEEE TC, IEEE TPDS, and IEEE TDSC). He is the recipient of IEEE Smart Computing Early Career Award (2023) and ACM SIGCSE China Rising Star Award (2022).

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